

Detailed Classification of Sectors by Immigration Intensity

We report here the full list of immigration intensive sectors by country, in the original language of each survey. We also report, in parenthesis, a brief note on each sector that was shown to respondents to better select the most appropriate sector. See Appendix A-3 for sources and definitions.

U.S.:

- Farming, fishing, and forestry occupations (farmers, fishers, agricultural workers etc.)
- Building and grounds cleaning and maintenance occupations (maids and housekeeping cleaners, janitors, building cleaning workers, grounds maintenance workers etc.)
- Construction and extraction occupations (painters, construction and maintenance, plumbers, electricians, extraction workers etc.)
- Computer and mathematical occupations (all the occupations related to mathematics, data and IT management, such as statisticians, web developers, computer programmers, actuaries, etc.)
- Production occupations (all the occupations related to the following sectors: industrial and artisanal production of goods, materials and components of any kind, industrial and artisanal food production, laundry, dry cleaning, sewing and tailoring, shoe making, woodworking, energy, petroleum and gas production, water operation, jewels and metal working etc.)
- Life, physical, and social science occupations (animal, food, soil and plant scientists, biochemists, medical scientists, physicists, chemists, economists, political scientist, sociologists, psychologists, historians etc.)
- Food preparation and serving related occupations (chefs and cooks, waiters, fast food workers, dishwashers, food servers etc.)
- Occupations related to transportation and material moving (truck, bus, train and taxi drivers, pilots, flight attendants, rail transportation workers, movers, delivery workers, gas station operators etc.)
- Occupations related to personal care, childcare and leisure (hairdressers, barbers and related, makeup artists, cosmetologists and related, personal care aides, childcare workers, all the occupations related to leisure and entertainment, like sport and gaming, cinemas, etc.)
- Healthcare support occupations (such as home health aides, nursing assistants, physical therapist assistants, dental or medical assistants etc.)

U.K.:

- Domestic personnel (maids, cooks, waiters, valets, butlers, laundresses, gardeners, gatekeepers, stable-lads, chauffeurs, caretakers, governesses, babysitters, tutors, secretaries etc.)
- Accommodation and food services (hotels, camping activities, restaurants, catering, bars, clubs)
- Transport and storage (land, water and air transport, warehousing, postal activities)

- Information and communication (publishing, music and video production and distribution, broadcasting, telecommunications, computer programming, data processing, news agencies)
- Administrative and support service activities (rental and leasing activities, employment agencies, travel agencies, security and investigation activities, cleaning activities, office administrative and support activities)
- Manufacturing (food and beverages products, textiles, wood products, printing and media reproduction, petroleum related products, chemical and pharmaceutical products, plastic and metal products, computers, machinery, vehicles, furniture...)
- Professional, scientific and technical activities (legal and accounting activities, management, architectural and engineering activities, research and development, veterinary activities)
- Health and social work (hospital activities, medical and dental practices, residential care and social work activities)
- Financial and insurance activities (banking, investment activities, insurance, pension funding, and auxiliary activities)

France:

- Ouvriers non qualifiés de type artisanal (inclut les apprentis; effectuant des tâches telles que: le gros et second œuvre du bâtiment (sauf travaux publics); l'entretien des automobiles, véhicules utilitaires, bâtiments, ascenseurs et machines de bureau; le dépannage d'appareils électroménagers; la fabrication non industrielle d'habillement; le nettoyage de locaux (sauf écoles et hôpitaux, et sauf domestique))
- Personnels des services directs aux particuliers (comprenant entre autres: service hôtelier; service en salle des restaurants; soins corporels d'hygiène et d'esthétique; garde d'enfants hors crèches; travail domestique chez des particuliers; concierges et gardiens d'immeubles)
- Commerçants et assimilés (salariés de leur entreprise; hôteliers-restaurateurs, fleuristes, poissonniers, prestataires de services)
- Ouvriers qualifiés de type artisanal (mêmes secteurs d'activité que pour les employés non qualifiés de type artisanal, mais pour des tâches nécessitant une formation spéciale; inclut les chefs d'équipe et contremaîtres)
- Artisans (salariés de leur entreprise, qui doit être de moins de 10 salariés; exclut les photographes)
- Ouvriers agricoles (agriculture, exploitation forestières, aquaculture, pêche; sont exclus les techniciens et agents de maîtrise)
- Ouvriers non qualifiés de type industriel (installation de machines, travail en laboratoire, travail des métaux et du bois; montage d'éléments mécaniques, production de matériels électriques et électroniques; contrôle de fabrication; réglage et entretien d'équipements industriels; travaux publics; mines et carrières; manutention; le tri, l'emballage et l'expédition)
- Policiers et militaires (comprend aussi les gardiens de l'administration pénitentiaire, les pompiers, et les agents de sécurité et de surveillance)

- Professions de l'information, des arts et des spectacles (bibliothécaires, conservateurs, journalistes, auteurs, directeurs d'édition ou d'audiovisuel, cadres artistiques, artistes musicaux, plasticiens, de la danse, du cirque)
- Chauffeurs (exclut les conducteurs de tramway et d'engins spéciaux de manutention ou de l'agriculture; inclut les livreurs et coursiers à pied et à vélo)
- Professeurs, professions scientifiques (enseignants du secondaire et supérieur, cadres de l'enseignement (dont inspecteurs, psychologues scolaires), employés de la recherche publique, médecins et pharmaciens sans activité libérale)
- Ouvriers qualifiés de type industriel (même activités que pour les ouvriers non qualifiés de type industriel, mais pour des tâches nécessitant une formation spéciale)

Italy:

- Venditori ambulanti (che operano in mercati o in altri luoghi pubblici, quali stazioni, fiere etc.)
- Servizi di assistenza (assistenza e cura di bambini, anziani o disabili, a casa o in strutture specializzate; questa categoria include, ad esempio, babysitter e badanti)
- Pulizia e lavori domestici (pulizia o altre mansioni in residenze private o in luoghi pubblici, quali hotel, uffici, ospedali, mezzi di trasporto pubblici etc.)
- Preparazione di cibo veloce e personale di supporto in cucina (quali pizzaioli, cuochi in ristoranti fast food, assistenti in cucina, lavapiatti, etc.)
- Agricoltura, allevamento, pesca e giardinaggio (quali agricoltori e lavoratori agricoli, pescatori, allevatori, giardinieri etc.)
- Trasporti commerciali e logistica (quali autotrasportatori, magazzinieri etc.)
- Metalmeccanici, meccanici e lavoratori nell'industria mineraria (addetti alla lavorazione del metallo e produzione di oggetti in metallo, riparazione di veicoli di vario tipo e macchinari, minatori e lavoratori in cave etc.)
- Edilizia (muratori, imbianchini etc.)
- Netturbini e spazzini (addetti alla pulizia di strade e piazze e alla raccolta di rifiuti)
- Turismo e ristorazione (quali lavoratori nel settore del turismo, cuochi, camerieri e baristi)
- parrucchieri ed estetiste, custodi, governanti, lavoratori che si occupano della cura di animali e altri lavoratori che si occupano di servizi alla persona)
- Lavorazione di cibo, lavorazione del legno, produzione di capi di abbigliamento a livello artigianale (macellai, fornai, pescivendoli, falegnami, sarti, calzolai, lavoratori di pellame etc.)
- Trasporti (autisti di veicoli civili che trasportano passeggeri, quali aerei, treni, navi, taxi, autobus, tram etc., e altro personale che lavora nel settore dei trasporti, quali assistenti di volo, controllori etc.)

- Manifatturiero - Operai (operai e operai specializzati che svolgono diverse mansioni in fabbrica)

Germany:

- Verkehr, Logistik, Schutz und Sicherheit (Verkehrs- und Logistikberufe, Führer/innen von Fahrzeug- und Transportgeräten, Schutz-, Sicherheits- und Überwachungsberufe, Gerichts- und Justizvollzug, Reinigungsberufe usw.)
- Rohstoffgewinnung, Produktion und Fertigung (alle Tätigkeiten in der Rohstoffgewinnung und -aufbereitung, Glas-, Metall-, Kunststoff-, Holz- und Keramikherstellung und -verarbeitung, Papier- und Druckberufe, technische Mediengestaltung, Metallbauberufe, Maschinen- und Fahrzeugtechnikberufe usw.)
- Kaufmännische Dienstleistungen, Warenhandel, Vertrieb, Hotel und Tourismus (Einkaufs-, Verkaufs-, Vertriebs- und Handelsberufe, sowie Tourismus-, Hotel- und Gaststättenberufe usw.)
- Bau, Architektur, Vermessung und Gebäudetechnik (Bauplanungs-, Architektur- und Vermessungsberufe, Hochbau- Tiefbau- und (Innen-)Ausbauberufe, sowie Gebäude- und versorgungstechnische Berufe usw.)

Sweden:

- Transport (arbete med passagerartrafik som tåg, buss och taxi, med godstrafik, flyttjänster, magasinering, postutdelning m.m.)
- Hotell och restaurang (arbete på hotell och annan logiverksamhet, bar, catering och restaurang)
- Information och kommunikation (arbete på förlag, med film, tv-program, telekommunikation, dataprogrammering, informationstjänster m.m.)
- Offentlig förvaltning m.m. (arbete inom offentlig förvaltning med ledning, administration m.m., med polis och domstolsverksamhet, försvaret, utrikesförvaltning m.m.)
- Utbildning (lärare på förskola, grundskola, gymnasium, körskola m.m., arbete med arbetsmarknadsutbildning, universitets- och högskoleutbildning m.m.)